

CLIMAAX
climate ready regions

Deliverable Phase 2 – Climate risk assessment

"Towards Climate Resilience: Assessing Silistra's Climate Challenges and Solutions"

(TOR: Towards Climate Resilience)

Bulgaria, Silistra

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1. Document Information

Deliverable Title	Phase 2 – Climate risk assessment
Brief Description	Phase 2 of the CLIMAAX project for Silistra Municipality focuses on refining and expanding the Climate Risk Assessment developed in Phase 1, with the aim of producing more robust and decision-relevant results. The phase deepens the analysis of priority hazards, particularly river flooding and heavy rainfall, while extending the assessment to additional climate risks relevant for the municipality, such as drought and extreme temperatures. The analysis explicitly considers short-, medium- and long-term time horizons in line with the CLIMAAX Handbook. By combining European climate information with local data and knowledge, Phase 2 delivers a refined multi-risk picture tailored to Silistra’s specific socio-economic and territorial context. The results provide a solid evidence base for prioritising climate risks and directly support the identification of adaptation options in Phase 3.
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2. Table of contents

Contents

1. Document Information	2
2. Table of contents	3
3. List of figures	4
4. List of tables	4
5. Abbreviations and acronyms	5
6. Executive summary	6
1 Introduction	8
1.1 Background	8
1.2 Main objectives of the project	8
1.3 Project team	9
1.4 Outline of the document's structure	9
2 Climate risk assessment – phase 2	10
2.1 Scoping	10
2.1.1 Objectives.....	11
2.1.2 Context	11
2.1.3 Participation and risk ownership.....	18
2.1.4 Application of principles	22
2.1.5 Stakeholder engagement	22
2.2 Risk Exploration	23
2.2.1 Screen risks (selection of main hazards)	23
2.2.2 Choose Scenario	26
2.3 Regionalized Risk Analysis	27
2.3.1 River floods	27
2.3.2 Heavy rainfall	28
2.3.3 Agricultural Drought	28
2.3.4 Wind.....	29
2.3.5 Snow.....	29
2.4 Key Risk Assessment Findings	29
2.4.1 Mode of engagement for participation	30
2.4.2 Gather output from Risk Analysis step	31
2.4.3 Assess Severity	31
2.4.4 Assess Urgency.....	33

2.4.5 Understand Resilience Capacity.....	35
2.4.6 Decide on Risk Priority.....	36
2.5 Monitoring and Evaluation.....	40
2.6 Work plan Phase 3.....	43
3 Conclusions Phase 2 - Climate risk assessment.....	45
4 Progress evaluation.....	47
5 Supporting documentation.....	50
6 References.....	51

3. List of figures

4. List of tables

Table 2.1. Institutional mapping and allocation of responsibilities within the CLIMAAX climate risk assessment process (Municipality of Silistra)

Table 2.2. Phase 2 risks

Table 2.3 – Key Risks Dashboard

Table 2.4. CLIMAAX Key Risk Assessment – Final prioritisation for Silistra

Table 2.5. Monitoring framework

Table 2.6. Monitoring indicators

Table 3.1. Overall prioritisation of climate risks for the municipality of Silistra

Table 4.1 Overview key performance indicators

Table 4.2 Overview milestones

5. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
BGN	Bulgarian Leva
CLIMAAX	CLIMAtE risk and vulnerability Assessment framework and toolbox project
CRA	Climate Risk Assessment
EEA	European Environmental Agency
EU	European Union
IFP	Individual Follow-up Plan
IME	Institute of Market Economics
MIDP	Municipal Integrated Development Plan
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
SPA	Spatial Planning Act

6. Executive summary

This deliverable presents the results of Phase 2 of the CLIMAAX Climate Risk Assessment (CRA) for Silistra Municipality. The document was developed to refine and deepen the initial risk screening conducted in Phase 1 by applying a harmonised, science-based and locally adapted methodology for assessing current and future climate risks at municipal level. It addresses the need for actionable, policy-relevant climate risk information that can support local decision-making, disaster risk reduction and long-term climate adaptation planning. Readers will gain a comprehensive overview of the main climate risks affecting Silistra Municipality, their relative severity and urgency, and the municipality's capacity to respond.

During Phase 2, the project focused on the extension and refinement of the multi-risk assessment using the CLIMAAX Common Methodology Framework and Toolbox. The analysis combined European-scale climate datasets with locally available data on exposure, vulnerability and critical infrastructure. The assessment concentrated on the most relevant climate hazards for Silistra Municipality, including river flooding, heavy rainfall, drought, snow and strong winds. Hazard-specific workflows were fine-tuned to the local context, enabling the identification of spatial patterns of risk and the differentiation between current and future risk levels under selected climate scenarios.

The main results of Phase 2 demonstrate that climate risks in Silistra Municipality are unevenly distributed across the territory and sectors, with river flooding and heavy rainfall emerging as the most critical hazards due to their potential for significant material damage, disruption of transport and public services, and impacts on vulnerable population groups. Drought and extreme temperature-related processes affect agricultural productivity and water resources, while snow and strong winds pose recurring challenges for mobility, infrastructure reliability and emergency response, particularly during winter periods. The assessment highlights a clear increase in risk severity for several hazards under future climate conditions, underscoring the need for anticipatory action.

A key outcome of this phase is the structured evaluation of risks based on severity, urgency and resilience capacity. This approach enabled the prioritisation of risks and provided a transparent basis for identifying where immediate action, further monitoring or longer-term adaptation planning is required. The analysis also revealed that, while basic emergency response mechanisms and sectoral plans are in place, adaptive capacity is constrained by ageing infrastructure, limited financial resources, and insufficient integration of climate projections into local planning instruments.

Phase 2 contributes directly to the overall objectives of the CLIMAAX project by strengthening the link between climate risk assessment and local governance. The results provide a robust evidence base that can support updates of municipal disaster protection programmes, spatial planning decisions and sectoral strategies. The use of the CLIMAAX Handbook ensured methodological consistency, transparency and comparability with other European regions, while the inclusion of local data increased the relevance and usability of the findings for Silistra Municipality.

In conclusion, Phase 2 confirms that Silistra Municipality faces increasing climate-related risks that require a shift from reactive disaster response towards proactive and integrated climate adaptation. The key takeaway is the necessity to prioritise high-risk hazards, address identified capacity gaps and systematically embed climate risk considerations into municipal planning and investment decisions.

The final phase of the project (Phase 3) will build on these findings by exploring and assessing potential adaptation options. It will focus on translating prioritized risk assessment outcomes into concrete, feasible and locally appropriate adaptation measures, in close cooperation with stakeholders and competent authorities.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Silistra Municipality is located in northeastern Bulgaria, along the southern bank of the Danube River, and forms part of the Danube macro-region. Its geographic position, predominantly flat relief, fertile agricultural land, and direct exposure to one of Europe's largest river systems define both its development potential and its structural vulnerability to climate-related hazards. The municipality has a predominantly rural and agricultural profile, combined with unfavorable socio-economic trends, including population decline, aging demographics, limited economic diversification, and comparatively low income levels. According to national and regional socio-economic indicators, Silistra is among the most vulnerable districts in Bulgaria in terms of economic resilience and adaptive capacity. These characteristics amplify the potential impacts of climate hazards, particularly floods, droughts, and extreme weather events, on livelihoods, infrastructure, and public services.

Climate change already manifests locally through increasing temperature extremes, prolonged dry periods, and episodes of intense precipitation. Due to its proximity to the Danube River and the presence of low-lying floodplains, Silistra is structurally exposed to river flooding, while its strong dependence on agriculture increases sensitivity to droughts, heat stress, and heavy rainfall. At the same time, limited financial and technical resources constrain the municipality's ability to respond proactively to escalating climate risks. Within this context, Silistra Municipality joined the CLIMAAX initiative to establish a structured, science-based, and locally grounded Climate Risk Assessment (CRA) that supports informed decision-making and long-term climate resilience.

During Phase 1, the municipality successfully applied the CLIMAAX Common Methodological Framework for the first time, focusing on two priority hazards—river floods and heavy rainfall—as pilot workflows. This phase validated the applicability of the CLIMAAX approach to the local context, tested the availability and usability of data, engaged key stakeholders, and generated preliminary risk insights. Importantly, Phase 1 created a shared understanding of climate risks among municipal actors and revealed critical data gaps and capacity needs that directly inform the next stage of work. Phase 2 builds on these achievements by moving from initial testing to refinement, expansion, and deepening of the multi-risk assessment, in line with the CLIMAAX Handbook's iterative logic.

1.2 Main objectives of the project

The main objective of Phase 2 is to refine and expand the Climate Risk Assessment for Silistra Municipality by strengthening the analytical depth, improving the spatial and socio-economic resolution of the assessment, and extending the analysis to additional climate hazards of high relevance for the territory.

While Phase 1 focused on validating the methodology and generating preliminary findings, Phase 2 is designed to increase robustness, comparability, and decision relevance of the results. This phase directly responds to the key lessons learned in Phase 1, particularly regarding the need for better integration of local data, socio-economic vulnerability indicators, and cross-hazard interactions.

Specifically, Phase 2 aims to:

- Refine risk estimates for the already analyzed hazards (river floods and heavy rainfall) using improved local datasets and stakeholder input;
- Extend the CRA to other priority hazards for Silistra, such as drought, wind and snow-related events, in accordance with the CLIMAAX risk exploration logic;
- Strengthen the assessment of exposure and vulnerability by integrating socio-economic characteristics, critical infrastructure, and land-use patterns at municipal and sub-municipal level;
- Improve the temporal dimension of the analysis by explicitly addressing short-, medium- and long-term risk horizons relevant for municipal planning.

The use of the CLIMAAX Handbook in Phase 2 ensures methodological consistency, transparency, and alignment with EU-level climate risk assessment standards. The Handbook's stepwise approach allows Silistra to systematically move from hazard screening and scenario selection toward more policy-relevant risk outputs. A key added value of Phase 2 is the enhanced use of local data and models, including municipal sectoral statistics (especially for agriculture and infrastructure), and locally observed impacts of past climate events. This integration significantly reduces uncertainty and allows the CRA to reflect Silistra's specific socio-economic and territorial context, rather than relying solely on generalized European datasets. Ultimately, Phase 2 serves as the analytical bridge between risk identification and the subsequent identification of adaptation options, ensuring that future measures are grounded in a solid and locally validated evidence base.

1.3 Project team

The project is implemented by a multidisciplinary team coordinated by external experts from "D and D Consulting" Ltd., Silistra Municipality, combining administrative, financial, environmental, and scientific expertise. The core team includes municipal experts responsible for project coordination, financial management, and environmental analysis, supported by external climate and risk assessment specialists and a subcontractor with experience in applying the CLIMAAX methodology. This combination ensures both institutional ownership and technical quality of the assessment.

1.4 Outline of the document's structure

This document is structured to reflect the logic of Phase 2 of the CLIMAAX Climate Risk Assessment and to clearly demonstrate how the work builds upon the results of Phase 1.

Following this introduction, the report presents:

- a refined description of the methodological approach applied in Phase 2, including data sources and scenario choices;
- an expanded multi-risk analysis covering additional climate hazards relevant for Silistra;
- an updated assessment of exposure, vulnerability, and risk interactions;
- key refined risk findings, highlighting priority risks and emerging trends across different time horizons.

The final sections synthesize the implications of the Phase 2 results for future adaptation planning and outline how these findings will feed directly into Phase 3 activities focused on the identification and prioritization of adaptation measures.

2 Climate risk assessment – phase 2

2.1 Scoping

The second phase of the climate risk assessment for the municipality of Silistra builds on the results of Phase 1 and builds on the already validated applicability of the CLIMAAX methodology in the local context. While the first phase aimed to test the approach by analyzing a limited number of climate hazards, the current stage aims to expand and deepen the assessment. The main objective of Phase 2 is to carry out a comprehensive multi-risk climate assessment that takes into account both current and future manifestations of climate hazards on the territory of the municipality of Silistra. The analysis is aimed at a better understanding of the impacts on the population, infrastructure, economic activities and the environment, as well as at identifying vulnerable groups and areas with increased risk. The scope of the assessment includes the entire territory of the municipality, with a more detailed analysis of areas with concentration of risks, in this case the Danube regions, agricultural areas and settlements with vulnerable infrastructure, if necessary. The time horizon of the analysis covers current climate conditions, as well as medium- and long-term scenarios for the future development of climate risks, depending on the available data and models within CLIMAAX. In Phase 2, special attention is paid to the characteristics of climate hazards, in terms of their frequency, intensity and potential changes over time. Such an analysis is also necessary in view of the needs of prevention, early warning systems and disaster preparedness. The analysis also considers the impacts on socio-economic development, laying the foundation for subsequent planning of measures, coordination between institutions and effective communication with the population. The identification and assessment process, as well as planning in Phase 2, is carried out in close cooperation with stakeholders. The accumulated experience and feedback from Phase 1 support a more precise selection of scenarios and workflows, which will be discussed in the following sections of the report. The scope of the analysis is clearly defined in terms of the territory (Silistra municipality), the key systems (population, agriculture, infrastructure and services), the scale of decision-making (municipal level with a link to regional and national frameworks) and the time horizon (from short-term to long-term), which ensures quality and consistency of the scoping stage according to the CLIMAAX framework. Key stakeholders include:

- ✓ Municipal administration – departments responsible for environment, urban planning, infrastructure, social services, emergency management and strategic development;
- ✓ Public service and infrastructure operators – water supply and sewerage company, transport operators, energy and district heating providers, and waste management services;
- ✓ Emergency and civil protection authorities – fire safety services, disaster response units and flood risk management authorities;
- ✓ Regional and national institutions – representatives of regional administrations, environmental authorities and agencies responsible for water and river basin management;
- ✓ Economic actors and business representatives – industrial enterprises, logistics and port operators, agricultural producers and business associations;
- ✓ Scientific and expert community – universities, research institutes, climate and risk assessment experts;
- ✓ Civil society and non-governmental organisations – environmental NGOs, social organisations and community groups;

- ✓ Vulnerable and priority groups – elderly residents, low-income households and populations living in flood-prone or high-risk areas.

2.1.1 Objectives

The main objective of the Climate Risk Assessment (CRA) in Phase 2 is to provide a comprehensive and applicable basis for making informed management decisions at the local level in the municipality of Silistra. Building on the results of Phase 1, the current stage aims for a deeper understanding of climate risks, their dynamics and potential future manifestations, with a focus on practical consequences for the population, infrastructure, economy and environment. The risk assessment aims to prioritize the main climate hazards. The results of the analysis will be used as an analytical basis for reviewing and updating key municipal strategic documents, local planning, and future initiatives related to sustainable development and adaptation to climate change. In this way, the climate risk assessment becomes a tool for local government in supporting long-term strategic planning. At the same time, the scope of the assessment is determined by a number of limitations and challenges. Among the main limitations are mainly related to the quality and quantity of available data on the basis of which the model and the prognostic analysis are built. The data in some cases are incomplete or non-uniform local data, with different spatial resolutions of climate and geospatial datasets, and historical data are missing. An additional challenge is to engage a wide range of stakeholders and ensure a sustainable participatory process, especially on topics related to long-term climate risks.

These limitations are addressed by combining available European and national data sources within CLIMAAX, gradually expanding stakeholder participation and using the results of Phase 1 as a starting point for a more precise selection of scenarios and workflows. Where insufficient information is available for certain risks or impacts, this is clearly noted in the relevant sections of the analysis, for the sake of transparency and correctness of the assessment.

2.1.2 Context

The climate risk assessment carried out in Phase 2 is being developed in line with the strategic development framework of the Municipality of Silistra, defined in the Integrated Development Plan of the Municipality for the period 2021–2027 (updated 2024), developed on the basis of the Regional Development Act. The assessment details and to some extent builds on the existing analyses and priorities set out in the plan, by providing in-depth and structured information on climate risks, vulnerabilities and potential impacts on key sectors and territories. In this way, the assessment becomes an analytical tool that supports climate change risk management, sustainable use of resources and increasing the resilience of the municipality in social, economic and environmental aspects and, in this sense, the local development goals set in the Integrated Development Plan.

The Integrated Development Plan of the Municipality, as well as the Disaster Protection Plan of the Municipality, identify significant risks related to floods, droughts, extreme temperatures and other climatic phenomena. These planning documents do not provide (nor is this their task) a systematic multi-risk assessment that integrates climate projections, socio-economic vulnerabilities and spatial characteristics of the territory into a single framework for analysis and decision-making. In this

sense, the current project and the implementation of Phase 2 respond to the need for a better understanding and management of climate risks in the context of persistent demographic and economic challenges. The report considers climate risks not only from the perspective of emerging environmental problems, but as a factor that directly affects the sustainable development, social inclusion and economic stability of the municipality. Therefore, the climate risk assessment is developed within the existing governance and regulatory environment, in accordance with the derived local policies. The municipality's IDP sets out priorities aimed at sustainable development, climate change risk management, ecological agriculture, infrastructure and social sustainability. However, climate adaptation is not yet fully integrated as an analytically justified and systematically implemented element in all sectoral policies. CRA Phase 2 aims to fill this gap by providing structured information that can be used to update policies, implementation programs and project priorities.

The project identifies climate-vulnerable sectors, indicating which sectors will be most affected by climate change in the municipality of Silistra. These include agriculture, the water sector, technical and transport infrastructure, as well as social and health services. The relationship associated with the amplification of these sectoral impacts is derived and proven. The analysis also establishes that climate risks for the municipality of Silistra are formed under the influence of factors that go beyond the local level. The location of the municipality along the Danube River implies a strong dependence on processes and decisions at the Danube basin level, including transboundary hydrological and climatic dynamics. National legislation, national and European policies, strategies and investment programs have an additional impact. Within this context, the report identifies that possible adaptation interventions include both structural and non-structural solutions. They include improving early warning and preparedness systems, integrating climate risks into spatial and investment planning, sustainable management of water, soil, energy and agricultural resources, as well as measures to increase administrative and public capacity. CRA Phase 2 creates the analytical basis on which these interventions can be prioritized and translated into concrete policies and projects, as indicated and in line with the priorities set out in the Municipality's Integrated Development Plan /IDP/.

The Climate Change Mitigation Act regulates the framework for national climate policy, including the planning, coordination and reporting of mitigation and adaptation measures at the national level without exhaustively defining specific powers and obligations for municipalities. This reflects the understanding that climate policy is part of a broader system of multi-level governance, in which the local level operates within the framework of nationally defined goals and priorities. In this context, the role of municipalities and mayors is manifested indirectly, through the integration of national climate goals into local strategic and spatial planning, territorial management, infrastructure and public services, as well as through the implementation of measures for adaptation to climate risks. Although these functions are not explicitly regulated in the law, they arise from the general powers of local authorities, from the obligations under sectoral legislation (disasters, spatial planning, environment) and from the practical need to implement climate policies at the territorial level. It is at the municipal level that the real impacts of climate risks manifest themselves, which makes municipalities a key implementer and mediator between national policy and local communities.

The climate risk assessment for the municipality of Silistra is developed within a clearly outlined national strategic and political framework, which places climate change adaptation, risk management and sustainable territorial development among the leading priorities of public policies.

This framework is formed by mutually complementary strategic documents that define both the long-term vision for the development of the country and the specific sectoral and territorial commitments at the national and local levels. At the highest strategic level, the National Development Program "Bulgaria 2030" defines the vision for sustainable, balanced and inclusive development, explicitly taking into account territorial differences and the vulnerability of individual regions to economic, social and environmental risks. Climate change and extreme weather events are considered as a systemic factor that affects the achievement of national goals and requires an integrated approach, including risk management, infrastructure resilience and protection of vulnerable communities. In this context, Bulgaria 2030 emphasizes the role of local authorities as key implementers of national priorities and the need for analytical tools to support decision-making at the territorial level.

At the sectoral level, the Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (INECP) 2021–2030 specifies Bulgaria's commitments regarding climate policies, positioning climate risk as a horizontal theme affecting energy, infrastructure, land use and social sustainability. While the main focus of the plan is on climate change mitigation and energy transition, INECP clearly recognizes the need for adaptation as an integral part of sustainable development. Particular importance is given to water resources management, infrastructure protection and increasing resilience to extreme climate events – priorities that are directly relevant to the municipality of Silistra, given its location along the Danube River and the risks of river floods and intense rainfall identified in Phase 1.

Complementary and explicitly aimed at risk management is the National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change and the Action Plan until 2030, which defines adaptation as a key priority of the national policy. All these national documents place a strong emphasis on the role of municipalities as the main level for implementing adaptation and climate risk management policies, while recognizing the limited administrative and analytical capacity of smaller and peripheral municipalities. In this sense, the municipality of Silistra, characterized by demographic decline, an aging population and high dependence on climate-sensitive economic sectors, is exposed to increased socio-economic consequences of climate risks. The flood and heavy rainfall hazards identified in Phase 1 act as a multiplier factor of the existing vulnerability, making a systematic and in-depth risk assessment necessary. The Integrated Development Plan (IDP) is the main tool for implementation of national strategic priorities at the local level and ensures the direct link between the long-term vision for the development of the country and specific territorial interventions in the municipality. The IPD was developed in accordance with the Spatial Development Act and the Methodological Guidelines of the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works and explicitly declares coherence with the National Development Program "Bulgaria 2030", the Integrated Energy and Climate Plan, the National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change, as well as with European and regional policies for sustainable development.

In this context, climate risks are not considered as an isolated environmental problem, but as a factor that influences economic development, social sustainability and demographic processes in the municipality. This is particularly relevant for Silistra, where adverse demographic trends and socio-economic vulnerability amplify the potential impacts of climate hazards.

At the operational level, the IPD concretizes the national objectives through clearly defined priorities and measures that are directly relevant to climate change adaptation and risk management. Within Priority 2: Connectivity and access to sustainable and ecological development, the IPD explicitly addresses climate change risk management as a stand-alone objective. Objective 2.1 "Development

of ecological and sustainable agriculture and climate change risk management” and the related Measure 3.7 “Climate change risk management” represent a direct territorial interpretation of the national priorities set out in the National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change. These provisions create a framework for the implementation of preventive and adaptation approaches at the local level, including with regard to flood risks and intense precipitation, identified as leading climate hazards for the municipality of Silistra in Phase 1 of the climate risk assessment.

The social aspect of the IPD is also particularly important, reflecting the understanding set out in Bulgaria 2030 that climate risks disproportionately affect vulnerable groups of the population. Priorities related to human potential development, social inclusion and access to services create prerequisites for reducing social vulnerability and increasing the capacity of the community to respond to and adapt to climate shocks. In summary, the Silistra Municipality’s IPD is the key unit through which the national strategic goals in the field of climate, adaptation and sustainable development are translated into specific local priorities, measures and investment intentions. The climate risk assessment within Phase 2 builds on this framework by providing analytical depth and structured information on specific climate hazards, vulnerabilities and impacts. In summary, the Silistra Municipality has an established integrated territorial development framework, implemented through the Integrated Development Plan of the municipality and the envisaged participation in Integrated Territorial Investments, as well as with clearly formulated environmental and climate-relevant priorities related to the sustainable use of resources, climate change risk management and the development of infrastructure and agriculture. At the same time, there is currently no systematic, multi-risk climate assessment that would integrate the relationship between climate hazards, socio-economic and spatial vulnerability and potential impacts, as well as provide an analytical basis for prioritizing territories and sectors. Such a solution is provided by CRA Phase 2.

Silistra District is characterized by a clearly expressed agrarian and territorially sensitive profile, determined by its geographical location along the Danube River and the predominant agricultural use of the land. The territory of the district covers 2,846 sq. km, with the utilized agricultural area reaching 1,652,839 decares, of which over 1,494,000 decares are arable land. Over 87% of the arable land is occupied by grain and technical crops, mainly wheat and sunflower, which determines a strong dependence of the economy and landscape on climatic conditions. The soil diversity in the area, dominant chernozems, alluvial meadow and peat-swamp soils in the Danube areas, creates prerequisites for high sensitivity to intense rainfall and river floods. The large share of arable land and the limited presence of permanently grassed areas and natural buffers increase the risk of surface runoff, soil erosion and loss of productivity in extreme climatic events, identified as leading risks in Phase 1 of the climate assessment.

From a demographic point of view, the municipality of Silistra is characterized by a decreasing and aging population, negative natural and mechanical growth and permanent migration of young people to larger economic centers. These processes lead to a shrinking local labor market, limited human capital and increased dependence on social and public services. The demographic structure increases the vulnerability of the municipality to external shocks, including climate extremes, as a significant part of the population belongs to sensitive age and social groups.

The economic profile of the municipality is dominated by agriculture and related activities, including the food industry. Agricultural production is mainly concentrated on cereals and oilseeds, with income and employment being highly dependent on climatic conditions, rainfall patterns and temperature fluctuations. The economy is characterized by relatively low diversification, limited

investments and lower added value, which reduces the capacity for adaptation to long-term climate change.

The infrastructure profile of the municipality shows uneven development and accumulated deficits, especially with regard to the road network, water supply and sewage infrastructure in smaller settlements. Part of the infrastructure is outdated and vulnerable to extreme rainfall, flooding and temperature amplitudes. This increases the risk of service disruption and complicates the response to climate-related disasters. The social profile of the municipality of Silistra is characterized by higher levels of poverty and social vulnerability compared to the national average. Access to health services, social infrastructure and specialized support is limited, especially in rural areas. Combined with an aging population, this makes the social system particularly sensitive to climate events such as heat waves, floods and disruptions of essential services.

The social sector and public health are indirectly but significantly affected by climate change. The socio-economic analysis shows that the municipality of Silistra is characterized by high levels of poverty, an aging population and limited access to health services. Extreme temperatures, floods and service disruptions affect the most vulnerable groups – the elderly, children, people with chronic diseases and low incomes. Climate risks thus become a factor that deepens existing social inequalities and demographic challenges.

Agriculture is the leading economic sector in the municipality of Silistra and the main source of income and employment, but at the same time it is the most exposed to climate risks. The production of cereals, oilseeds, fruits and vegetables is highly dependent on the rainfall regime, temperatures and the frequency of extreme events. The established trends towards more frequent and prolonged droughts, alternating with intense rainfall and hailstorms, lead to direct crop losses, increased production costs and reduced economic stability of agricultural holdings. The climate risk in this sector is further amplified by the limited development of irrigation infrastructure and the decreasing number of active agricultural producers. The Monitoring Survey of Land Use in Bulgaria (BANSIK) 2025 report provides a reliable statistical picture of the structure of land use by districts and statistical regions, with Silistra District falling into the North Central region. The data clearly show that the region in which Silistra is located is characterized by a high share of utilized agricultural area and arable land, with cereals and oilseed crops occupying the majority of the cultivated areas. This type of land use implies a strong dependence on the rainfall regime, temperature fluctuations and extreme climatic events. The concentration of uniform crops on large areas increases vulnerability to intense rainfall and soil waterlogging, periods of drought and erosion processes and loss of soil fertility. In the context of the climate risks identified in Phase 1 (floods and intense rainfall), this land use acts as an amplifying factor of risk, especially in the low-lying and riparian parts of the territory.

The land use profile of the municipality of Silistra, characterized by a high concentration of arable land and a limited share of ecologically stabilizing territories, increases the sensitivity of the municipality to the identified climate risks of intense rainfall and flooding. /BANSIK 2025, FINAL RESULTS on the use of the territory of BULGARIA, https://www.mzh.government.bg/media/filer_public/2025/12/04/ra_465_publicationbancik2025.pdf/

Separately, data from the 2020 Census of Agricultural Holdings - <https://www.mzh.government.bg/bg/statistika-i-analizi/prebroyavane-na-zemedelskite->

[stopanstva-prez-2020-g/](#) , recently published by the National Statistical Institute, provide additional information by showing that sustainable land and soil management is still not evenly distributed, which has a direct impact on the adaptive capacity of the agricultural sector.

In the context of the Silistra municipality, where agriculture is the leading economic sector and the main land user, this profile increases sensitivity to climate risks such as intense rainfall and flooding, especially in terms of soil erosion and loss of productivity. The food industry, which is closely linked to agriculture, is also vulnerable to climate change. Technical and transport infrastructure is another critically important sector exposed to climate impacts. Intense precipitation and river floods create a risk of damage to the road network, bridges, water supply and sewage systems, especially in areas with outdated or insufficiently maintained infrastructure. This is particularly significant for the municipality of Silistra, where the share of first-class roads is low and access to basic services in smaller settlements is limited. Climate extremes can lead to temporary disruption of transport links and the provision of basic services, which has a direct impact on economic activity and social connectivity.

The water sector is key for both the population and the economy of the municipality. The risk of river floods identified in Phase 1 affects not only the coastal areas along the Danube, but also the water supply infrastructure and the quality of water resources. At the same time, increasing droughts increase the pressure on available water sources, which may lead to problems with drinking water supply, especially in smaller and peripheral settlements. Municipality-Silistra falls into region BG1_APSFR_DU_001 with a significant potential risk of floods under Art. 146d of the Law on Floods, according to the preliminary assessment of the risk of floods due to the overflow of the Danube River, carried out by the Basin Directorate-Pleven as of 20.12.2011.

In summary, the sectors most relevant to the municipality of Silistra are highly interconnected and vulnerable to climate change. Climate impacts have the potential to exacerbate the region's already existing economic and social vulnerabilities, which highlights the need for an integrated, risk-based approach to planning adaptation measures within the CRA Phase 2.

Climate risks in the municipality of Silistra are significantly influenced by external factors that go beyond the administrative borders of the municipality. The most significant external influence stems from the location of the municipality along the Danube River, whose hydrological regime is determined by climate processes and management decisions throughout the Danube Basin. Intense precipitation, snowmelt and upstream water volume management can lead to increased water levels and the risk of river flooding in Silistra, regardless of local conditions and prevention measures.

An additional external influence is exerted by the transboundary nature of the region, including the land and river borders with Romania. Land use, agricultural practices and water management on both sides of the border are functionally linked, which means that climate impacts and the consequences of extreme events can have cumulative and transboundary effects. In addition, national and European policies and initiatives related to flood risk management, climate change adaptation and agricultural development create a framework of requirements and opportunities that influence the choice and implementation of measures at the local level. In this context, the climate risk assessment for the municipality of Silistra should take into account not only local characteristics, but also the broader regional and cross-border processes that shape the risk profile.

The main objective of the project is to increase the resilience of the municipality of Silistra to climate change and stems directly from the identified climate risks, as well as from the socio-economic and territorial profile of the municipality. The analysis shows that Silistra is highly vulnerable due to a combination of flat relief, high dependence on agriculture, proximity to the Danube River and the presence of vulnerable social groups. In this context, adaptation interventions should not be seen as separate technical measures, but as an integrated set of actions aimed at better understanding, managing and reducing climate risks in the long term.

First of all, targeted support is needed for the adaptation of agriculture, which is a key sector for the local economy, but also the most affected by climate change. Prolonged droughts and high temperatures are already leading to losses of agricultural land and reduced yields, while intense rainfall, hail and strong winds are causing significant damage to crops. The adaptation of agriculture to climate change in the municipality of Silistra should be seen as a long-term, systematic process aimed at increasing the resilience of agro-ecosystems to increasing climate extremes, and not just as a reaction to individual adverse events. The established trends towards longer droughts, higher temperatures and more frequent intense rainfall require adaptation measures that simultaneously address water deficit, soil vulnerability and the economic instability of agricultural holdings. In this context, a key adaptation priority is increasing the resilience of the water regime in agriculture. This includes not only investments in irrigation systems, but also a broader approach to the adaptation of water management, but also the implementation of water-saving technologies, local solutions for water retention and storage, as well as better coordination between agricultural practices and available water resources. The goal is not to increase water consumption, but to increase the efficiency and flexibility of systems in the face of increasing climate uncertainty. Adaptation to climate change also requires rethinking agricultural practices and land use with a view to reducing vulnerability to extreme precipitation, erosion and soil degradation. Promoting a greater diversity of crops and varieties better adapted to drought and temperature amplitudes, as well as the implementation of soil conservation and climate-smart practices, are key adaptation measures. In conditions of dominant crop production and high concentration of arable land, these measures are essential for reducing the systemic sensitivity of the sector to climate risks. Nature-based solutions that contribute to increasing ecosystem resilience and simultaneously reducing climate risks would also have a particularly important role in adaptation. Restoring permanent grasslands, ecological buffers and green belts, especially in low-lying and riparian areas, can improve water retention, limit surface runoff and mitigate the impact of intense precipitation. In this sense, part of the uncultivated lands and fallow lands represent a potential resource for adaptation, and not only an indicator of economic weakness. In conclusion, the adaptation of agriculture to climate change in the municipality of Silistra should be integrated, long-term and risk-based, combining technical, ecosystem, economic and management measures. Such an approach not only reduces the vulnerability of the sector to the identified climate risks, but also contributes to increasing the overall resilience of the local economy and territory in the conditions of a changing climate.

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2.1.3 Participation and risk ownership

The leading role in the process is played by the Municipality of Silistra, the Regional Directorate of Agriculture - Silistra and the Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Population Protection - Silistra, which were identified in Phase 1 as the main institutional responsibilities related to risk management. The municipal administration is actively involved in defining the objectives, access to data, coordination with strategic documents (IPD, disaster protection plan) and communication with local communities. The Regional Directorate of Agriculture provides expert information on climate impacts on agriculture, and the Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Population Protection - Silistra contributes with experience and data related to disaster response, early warning and population protection. Climate change mitigation policy in Bulgaria is centralized and formulated primarily at the national level, with key objectives, strategic documents and implementation mechanisms adopted by the Council of Ministers and competent state bodies. It regulates the framework for national climate policy, including the planning, coordination and reporting of mitigation and adaptation measures, but does not exhaustively define specific powers and obligations for municipalities.

Table 2.1. Institutional mapping and allocation of responsibilities within the CLIMAAX climate risk assessment process (Municipality of Silistra)

Institutional level	Institution / actor	Role in the CLIMAAX process	Main responsibilities	Linkages and coordination
National level	Council of Ministers of the Republic of Bulgaria	Policy-setting authority	Adoption of national climate change mitigation and adaptation objectives, strategies and implementation frameworks	Provides the overarching policy framework within which local and regional actors operate
National level	Competent national authorities (environment, disasters, spatial planning)	Regulatory and strategic coordination	Development and implementation of sectoral legislation and strategic documents related to climate change, disaster risk management and territorial planning	Vertical coordination with municipalities through sectoral legislation and planning instruments
Local level (lead)	Municipality of Silistra	Lead institution and de facto risk owner	Definition of objectives, access to local data, coordination with municipal strategic documents (PIRO, Disaster Protection Plan), implementation of adaptation measures and communication with local communities	Acts as intermediary between national climate policy and local stakeholders; coordinates all actors involved in Phases 1 and 2
Regional level	Regional Directorate of Agriculture – Silistra	Sectoral expert authority	Provision of expert information on climate impacts on agriculture, support to risk analysis related to agricultural production and land use	Cooperates with the Municipality of Silistra and local farmers; contributes to sector-specific vulnerability assessment
Regional level	Regional Directorate of Fire Safety and Population Protection – Silistra	Disaster risk management authority	Contribution of data and experience related to disaster response, early	Supports prevention, preparedness and response

			warning systems and population protection	components of the climate risk assessment
Civil society	Local NGOs, cultural and community organisations (e.g. women's organisations, environmental NGOs, community centres, schools)	Community intermediaries	Representation of local and social interests, identification of vulnerable groups, dissemination of information on climate risks and adaptation measures	Facilitate two-way communication between institutions and local communities
Private sector	Local enterprises (e.g. agriculture, processing, industry)	Economic stakeholders	Participation in consultations, provision of sector-specific information on climate exposure and impacts	Linked to the Municipality and sectoral authorities through targeted consultations
Local communities	Vulnerable groups and territories (low-lying Danube areas, old neighbourhood, farmers near rivers and ravines, elderly, children, socially vulnerable households)	Risk-exposed actors	Direct exposure to climate risks such as flooding, intense rainfall and disruption of basic services	Included through targeted communication, consultations and stakeholder engagement activities

The institutional framework for climate change mitigation and adaptation in Bulgaria is characterized by centralized policy formulation at national level and decentralized implementation at municipal level. Within the CLIMAAX climate risk assessment, this results in municipalities acting as de facto risk owners, as climate impacts, exposure and vulnerability are concentrated at the territorial level. While national authorities define strategic objectives and regulatory frameworks, municipalities integrate climate goals into local planning, infrastructure management and disaster risk reduction. This imbalance between risk ownership and available institutional capacity is a key factor in the assessment of response capacity and the prioritization of climate risks within the CLIMAAX methodology.

In the municipality of Silistra, the responsibility for identifying, assessing and managing risks is clearly regulated in the context of disaster situations, through the Municipal Disaster Protection Plan, developed in accordance with the Disaster Protection Act. The municipal administration, led by the mayor, has a leading role in coordinating the activities of risk analysis and assessment, planning preventive measures and integrating the results into local policies and plans. The plan provides for a systematic analysis of possible disasters, including floods, droughts, extreme rainfall, strong winds and snowfalls, as well as an assessment of their consequences for the population,

infrastructure, economy and environment. Measures to respond and limit the consequences of disasters are organized within the Unified Rescue System, with responsibilities distributed between the Municipality of Silistra, the Regional Directorate for Fire Safety and Population Protection, the regional administration and other competent institutions. The municipal administration, led by the mayor, has a leading role in coordinating activities for risk analysis and assessment, planning preventive measures and integrating the results into local policies and plans. The plan provides for a systematic analysis of possible disasters, including floods, droughts, extreme precipitation, strong winds, snowfall and other climate-related events, as well as an assessment of their consequences for the population, infrastructure, economy and environment. Measures to respond to and limit the consequences of disasters are organized within the Unified Rescue System, with responsibilities distributed between the Municipality of Silistra, the Regional Directorate for Fire Safety and Population Protection, the regional administration and other competent institutions. Legal entities, sole proprietors and farmers are responsible for implementing self-protection measures and maintaining emergency plans for sites and activities with increased risk. This model of shared responsibility reflects the understanding that managing climate risks requires coordinated actions between the public sector, emergency response services and business entities. This leads to an institutional “gray zone” in which climate risk is recognized but not always actively managed through current planning, investment decisions and sectoral policies. It is this gap between disaster management and long-term adaptation to climate change that determines the need to implement approaches such as CLIMAAX, which support municipalities to take risk ownership beyond disaster regimes. Through systematic risk assessment, stakeholder participation and integration of climate considerations into local governance, responsibility for climate risks is transformed from reactive to proactive and strategic.

The municipal disaster protection plan identifies specific territories and population groups that are particularly vulnerable to various types of disasters, including Danube areas, low-lying parts of settlements and areas with insufficient sewage and drainage infrastructure. The representation of these vulnerable groups in the planning and risk management processes is carried out through non-governmental organizations, community centers and local community structures that have direct contact with the population and know the local problems and needs. Socially vulnerable groups – the elderly, children, people with limited incomes and residents of old neighborhoods – are disproportionately affected by floods, prolonged power and water supply interruptions and extreme winter conditions. Farmers, especially those located near the Danube River, ravines and dams, represent another key priority group due to the risk of loss of harvest and economic infrastructure. Educational, cultural and environmental institutions complement this network by supporting the dissemination of information and the engagement of local communities.

The determination of acceptable and tolerable risk levels in the Municipality of Silistra is based on a qualitative assessment set out in the Municipal Disaster Protection Plan, rather than on pre-defined quantitative thresholds. The plan clearly outlines scenarios and damages that are considered unacceptable, such as affecting human life and health, flooding of residential areas, serious damage to critical infrastructure, disruption of basic services and significant losses to agriculture and the economy of the municipality.

In this context, the acceptable risk is considered as a function of the frequency and intensity of disaster events, the capacity for prevention and response and the possibilities for rapid recovery.

The analysis of actually occurring events, the identification of critical points and vulnerable areas, as well as the planned preparedness and response measures serve as a basis for assessing which risks can be temporarily tolerated and which require priority and long-term adaptation interventions. This is where the CLIMAAX climate risk assessment project contributes additional analytical depth, building on the existing framework and orienting it towards future climate challenges.

2.1.4 *Application of principles*

The determination of acceptable and tolerable risk levels in the Municipality of Silistra is based on a qualitative assessment set out in the Municipal Disaster Protection Plan, rather than on pre-defined quantitative thresholds. The plan clearly outlines scenarios and damages that are considered unacceptable, such as affecting human life and health, flooding of residential areas, serious damage to critical infrastructure, disruption of basic services and significant losses to agriculture and the economy of the municipality. In this context, the acceptable risk is considered as a function of the frequency and intensity of disaster events, the capacity for prevention and response and the possibilities for rapid recovery. The analysis of actually occurring events, the identification of critical points and vulnerable areas, as well as the planned preparedness and response measures serve as a basis for assessing which risks can be temporarily tolerated and which require priority and long-term adaptation interventions. This is where the CLIMAAX climate risk assessment project contributes additional analytical depth, building on the existing framework and orienting it towards future climate challenges.

- Social justice, equity and inclusivity: The analysis focused on vulnerable groups, including elderly populations, low-income households and rural communities, by explicitly considering differences in exposure and adaptive capacity across the municipality.
- Quality, rigour and transparency: The CLIMAAX Framework was applied consistently, with clear documentation of data sources, assumptions and methodological choices, combining European climate data with locally available information.
- Precautionary approach: High-impact climate risks such as floods and droughts were prioritised, and multiple time horizons were considered to support early and proactive adaptation planning despite remaining uncertainties.

2.1.5 *Stakeholder engagement*

The engagement of stakeholders in the CLIMAAX project for the municipality of Silistra is organized as a phased and building process, which begins in Phase 1 and continues purposefully in Phase 2 with a focus on deepening the analysis, validating the results and preparing for their practical implementation. The main goal of this process is not only to inform the participants, but also to actively involve institutions, experts, business and civil society in the identification of risks, vulnerable groups and applicable adaptation solutions.

Representatives of the municipal administration, regional state structures (including the Regional Directorate for Fire Safety and Population Protection and the Regional Directorate for Agriculture - Silistra), as well as external experts and representatives of the academic community, have participated in the meetings, seminars and communication activities held so far. Representatives of civil society, local business and agricultural producers who are directly affected by climate risks have also gradually been included in the process. Engagement is carried out through various formats

– kick-off meeting, press conference, thematic workshops, publications on the municipality's website and informal consultations. The project objectives and results were communicated in clear, non-technical language, tailored to different audiences, with more detailed methodological explanations provided for more expert groups. Particular emphasis was placed on linking the results of the climate analysis to real local problems, such as damage to agriculture, infrastructure and service disruptions in extreme events. This contributed to a better understanding of the importance of climate risk assessment and increased interest in the next stages of the project. The results of Phase 1 and Phase 2 were perceived by the participants as relevant and timely, but at the same time specific recommendations for improvement were made. Representatives of the local administration and environmental experts stressed the need for more detailed and up-to-date local data, as some of the available information is outdated or insufficiently precise, which limits the reliability of the assessment. It was recommended to expand monitoring and closer cooperation with scientific institutions.

Civil society organizations and business representatives expressed a desire for more active participation of the local community, especially farmers, entrepreneurs and other economic entities that are directly exposed to climate risks. Separately, the need for better coordination between institutions at the municipal, regional and national levels was noted, including through the establishment of a permanent coordination mechanism or working group.

The feedback received has already been reflected in the design of Phase 2, with the project focusing on collecting additional data, conducting a deeper analysis of social vulnerability and economic impacts, and developing more practically oriented recommendations. The results of the multi-risk assessment will be used to review and update municipal strategic documents, including disaster risk reduction programs and investment planning tools, as well as to prepare a long-term climate resilience strategy.

The main difficulties encountered in the process of stakeholder engagement are related to the limited availability of detailed local data, the different levels of expertise among the participants and the fragmented communication between institutions. An additional challenge is the translation of complex climate analyses into practically applicable solutions understandable to businesses and local communities. However, these difficulties are considered not as an obstacle, but as an important conclusion from Phase 1, which directs Phase 2 towards a more targeted engagement, better coordination and a stronger orientation towards the real needs of the municipality of Silistra.

In this way, stakeholder engagement in CLIMAAX moves from a consultative stage to a co-creation of knowledge and solutions, which is key for the sustainable implementation of the results.

2.2 Risk Exploration

2.2.1 Screen risks (selection of main hazards)

1. New developments compared to Deliverable 1

Phase 2 built on the preliminary screening conducted in Deliverable 1 by **refining hazard workflows and integrating local datasets**. Key new developments include:

- Incorporation of **high-resolution local exposure and vulnerability data**, including population density, socio-economic indicators, and critical infrastructure layers.

- Use of **Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) datasets** and downscaled climate projections to identify future changes in hazard frequency and intensity.
- Detailed **spatial mapping** of hazards (flood-prone areas, urban heat stress zones, drought-prone agricultural land) and their intersection with exposed and vulnerable assets.
- Refinement of the **priority risk list**, focusing on hazards that show the most pronounced future increases in severity and impact on the municipality.

Based on the updated Phase 2 analysis, the following climate-related hazards were identified as most relevant for Silistra Municipality:

- River flooding: Mainly affecting low-lying urban areas and floodplain settlements along the Danube tributaries.
- Heavy rainfall/short-duration intense precipitation: Leading to surface flooding in urban and peri-urban areas, causing traffic disruption and localized damage.
- Drought / prolonged dry periods: Impacting agricultural production (crops such as wheat, corn, and sunflower) and water supply systems.
- Snow and strong winds: Affecting transport infrastructure, utilities, and public services, particularly during winter months.

Rationale for selection: These hazards were selected due to their high frequency, observed and projected impact on population and critical sectors, and stakeholder concern. Other hazards, such as wildfires, were excluded as they are not significant for Silistra's geographical and land-use context.

- River flooding: Observed along the Danube tributaries; primarily affects residential areas in floodplains, municipal roads, and some industrial zones.
- Heavy rainfall: Causes localized flooding in urban neighborhoods with inadequate drainage. Municipal emergency services report recurring incidents.
- Drought: Already impacts crop yields and agricultural water supply, with increasing frequency over the last decade.
- Snow and strong winds: Disrupt transport (roads, rail) and municipal services, particularly in peripheral areas.

Tables and spatial maps from Phase 2 show hotspot locations for each hazard and overlay with population, infrastructure, and economic exposure. Severity levels are indicated in the risk matrices, with future scenarios projecting increased impacts for heatwaves, drought, and extreme rainfall.

- Observed hazards: Flood events, localized surface water accumulation, heatwave episodes, drought periods, occasional windstorms and snowstorms.
- Expected hazards (from CLIMAAX projections and Copernicus Atlas data): temperature increases: projected +2–3°C by 2041–2070 under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, increased frequency of extreme precipitation events, longer dry periods, particularly affecting summer months.

No other significant risks were identified.

Copernicus Atlas supports these projections by showing regional climate anomaly patterns in Silistra, highlighting increased heat stress and precipitation variability. Maps confirm that river floodplains and urban centers are particularly exposed to combined hazards.

For Phase 2, the following risks were prioritized for detailed assessment:

Table 2.2. Phase 2 risks

<i>Risk</i>	<i>Rationale</i>
River flooding	High material damage potential; affects population and infrastructure along low-lying areas.
Heavy rainfall	Frequent, localized events causing urban flooding and disruption of services.
Drought	Direct impact on agriculture, food processing, and water resources; high socio-economic relevance.
Snow / Strong winds	Operational challenges for transport and municipal services; recurrent hazard.

These risks were selected to ensure maximum relevance for municipal adaptation planning, focusing on those with observable impacts and high future severity projections.

Available data:

- Historical records from NIMH, river gauge stations, and municipal emergency reports.
- Local spatial datasets: population density, land use, critical infrastructure, sectoral vulnerability.
- CLIMAAX hazard workflows, including downscaled climate projections and scenario-based analysis.
- Phase 1 outputs: preliminary screening of hazards and vulnerable assets.

Knowledge gaps / further needs:

- High-resolution urban drainage and infrastructure vulnerability data.
- Quantitative socio-economic impact assessments for extreme precipitation and heatwaves.
- Updated local agricultural vulnerability data under climate change scenarios.
- Stakeholder validation of future scenario plausibility and tolerable risk levels.

Phase 2 Risk Exploration for Silistra Municipality has **refined the hazard selection and spatial prioritization** based on local context and stakeholder input. The results highlight **priority hazards with high current and future impacts**, identify exposure hotspots, and provide a foundation for Phase 3, where **adaptation measures will be developed** targeting the most critical risks.

2.2.2 Choose Scenario

For Silistra Municipality, future climate conditions were selected in line with the CLIMAAX Framework and based on the relevance of observed and projected climate trends for the Danube riverine and agricultural context of the region. The analysis focuses on climate conditions that are already affecting the municipality and are expected to intensify under future climate change.

The selected future climate conditions include:

- changes in precipitation patterns, characterised by longer dry periods combined with episodes of intense rainfall;
- increased probability and magnitude of river flooding linked to the Danube River and its tributaries;
- increasing average and extreme temperatures, leading to more frequency of drought conditions affecting agriculture, water availability and ecosystems.

These conditions were selected because they directly correspond to the priority hazards identified during Phase 1 and reflect the dominant climate risk drivers for Silistra. The choice of climate conditions follows the CLIMAAX recommendation to focus on **plausible, decision-relevant climate futures**, rather than exploring all possible scenarios.

Future socio-economic developments were defined using a combination of national statistical trends and the Institute for Market Economics (IME) report for 2025, which provides a detailed socio-economic profile of Silistra district.

The analysis considers the following key socio-economic trends:

- continued population decline and ageing, with Silistra among the districts with the most unfavourable demographic indicators in Bulgaria, leading to a shrinking labour force and increased dependency ratios;
- limited economic diversification, with a strong reliance on agriculture and low-value-added activities, increasing sensitivity to climate variability;
- persistently low income levels and investment capacity, constraining both private and public adaptation potential;
- high dependence on food production and agricultural supply chains, which are directly exposed to drought, heat stress and extreme precipitation;
- limited prospects for significant growth in food consumption, combined with potential increases in food prices driven by climate impacts on agricultural yields.

These socio-economic developments were selected because they significantly influence exposure and vulnerability, and because they are expected to persist or intensify over the coming decades, according to the IME analysis.

Future climate conditions and socio-economic developments were combined following the risk-based logic of the CLIMAAX Framework, where risk is understood as the interaction between hazard, exposure and vulnerability.

Rather than creating fully quantitative integrated scenarios, the project applied a scenario-consistent qualitative and quantitative approach, whereby:

- climate projections define the future hazard intensity and frequency;
- socio-economic trends determine changes in exposure (e.g. population distribution, land use, economic activities) and vulnerability (e.g. ageing population, economic capacity);
- the combined effects are analysed to identify how climate risks evolve over time.

For example, increasing drought frequency combined with declining and ageing rural populations leads to heightened vulnerability of agricultural systems and reduced adaptive capacity. Similarly, intensified precipitation and flood hazards, combined with limited municipal investment capacity, result in higher residual risk for infrastructure and settlements in flood-prone areas.

This approach ensures internal consistency between climate and socio-economic assumptions while remaining aligned with the data availability and scale of municipal decision-making.

In accordance with the CLIMAAX Handbook, the analysis considers multiple time horizons to capture the dynamic nature of climate risks and socio-economic change:

- Short-term horizon (up to 5 years): reflects near-term climate variability and current socio-economic conditions, supporting immediate planning and preparedness measures.
- Medium-term horizon (20–30 years): aligns with typical municipal planning cycles and demographic projections, capturing structural socio-economic changes and more pronounced climate trends.
- Long-term horizon (50+ years): explores the potential magnitude of climate risks under sustained warming and long-term demographic decline, supporting strategic and anticipatory thinking.

The use of multiple time horizons allows Silistra Municipality to understand not only current and emerging risks, but also how risk priorities may shift over time, providing a robust foundation for adaptation planning in Phase 3.

2.3 Regionalized Risk Analysis

Due to space limitations within the main body of Deliverable 2, the detailed hazard and risk assessments for the identified priority climate risks in the Municipality of Silistra are provided as separate annexes. These annexes document the full workflow implementation, including hazard modelling, vulnerability and exposure analysis, and quantitative risk estimation. The present section provides a concise synthesis of the applied methodologies and key outcomes for each hazard, with explicit references to the corresponding annexes.

2.3.1 River floods

The river flood risk analysis for the municipality of Silistra was carried out using hydrodynamic flood modelling for multiple return periods, covering both current climate conditions and future projections under different climate scenarios. The analysis assessed flood extent and depth, exposure of population, buildings, agricultural land and critical infrastructure, as well as associated economic losses and potential population displacement. The results show that the most affected areas are

located in the Aydemir lowland and along the Danube River, where significant flood depths, large numbers of exposed and displaced population, and high economic losses are projected, particularly for events with higher return periods.

Although climate projections do not indicate a substantial increase in flood depths in the future, the magnitude of current and projected impacts remains high due to the concentration of population, economic activities and land use in flood-prone areas. These findings indicate that river flooding constitutes a structurally important risk for Silistra municipality and provide a robust evidence base for the subsequent qualitative evaluation of severity, urgency and resilience capacity. Detailed results and maps are presented in **Annex A – River Floods**.

2.3.2 *Heavy rainfall*

The heavy rainfall risk analysis was conducted using indicators of short-duration and daily extreme precipitation, including projected changes in intensity and frequency under future climate scenarios. The assessment focused on exceedance of critical rainfall thresholds known to cause damage to buildings, transport infrastructure and drainage systems in both urban and rural areas of the municipality. The results indicate a clear increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme precipitation events across Silistra, particularly under high-emission scenarios, with projected rainfall amounts exceeding damage thresholds more frequently than in the historical period.

The spatially widespread nature of the projected changes and the increasing likelihood of disruptive rainfall events suggest growing future impacts on infrastructure and settlements. These outcomes highlight heavy rainfall as a risk with increasing relevance over time and justify further evaluation of its future severity, urgency and the adequacy of existing resilience measures in the key risk assessment. Detailed results are provided in **Annex B – Heavy Rainfall**.

2.3.3 *Agricultural Drought*

The agricultural drought analysis was performed using multiple combinations of global and regional climate models to assess future changes in precipitation, evapotranspiration and soil water availability, and their impacts on key crops cultivated in the municipality of Silistra. The assessment focused on rain-fed agriculture and evaluated potential yield reductions and associated economic losses for maize, wheat, sunflower and barley under future climate scenarios. The results consistently indicate substantial yield reductions for maize and sunflower by the end of the century, with corresponding economic losses and risks to the long-term viability of agricultural production.

While agricultural drought represents a slow-onset hazard, the scale and persistence of projected impacts suggest potentially systemic consequences for the local agricultural sector. These findings indicate that agricultural drought constitutes a major long-term risk and provide the analytical basis for subsequent assessment of future severity, urgency and resilience capacity in the key risk prioritisation process. Detailed analyses and results are presented in **Annex C – Agricultural Drought**.

2.3.4 Wind

The wind risk analysis for Silistra municipality was based on historical cyclone tracks, maximum wind gust estimates and an assessment of potential damage to the existing building stock and land use. The analysis shows that storms affecting the municipality typically pass north of the area and that maximum wind gusts remain relatively low due to the absence of orographic amplification. No significant damages were identified in the analysed scenarios, and estimated economic losses are negligible.

These results indicate that wind currently does not represent a major source of climate-related risk for Silistra municipality. Consequently, wind is considered of comparatively low relevance within the overall risk profile, a conclusion that is further examined in the qualitative key risk assessment. Detailed information is provided in **Annex D – Wind**.

2.3.5 Snow

The snow risk analysis was carried out using reanalysis data and climate model projections to assess the frequency of blizzards and heavy snowfall events, as well as the proportion of the population potentially affected. The results indicate that extreme snowfall events occur infrequently in the municipality of Silistra and that their frequency is projected to decrease towards the middle of the 21st century. Both historical and projected data suggest limited exposure of the population and relatively minor impacts compared to other assessed hazards.

Although snow events can cause temporary disruptions, their low frequency and declining future trends indicate a limited contribution to overall climate risk in the municipality. These findings support the subsequent qualitative evaluation of snow-related risks within the key risk assessment framework. Detailed results are included in **Annex E – Snow**.

2.4 Key Risk Assessment Findings

The assessment of key climate risks for the municipality of Silistra was conducted in accordance with the CLIMAAX Key Risk Assessment Protocol and builds directly on the results of the preceding risk analysis stage presented in Section 2.3 and the related annexes. The purpose of this step is not to identify new risks, but to interpret, compare and prioritise already identified climate risks by considering their relative importance for the municipality under current and future conditions.

The Key Risk Assessment evaluates risk outputs along three complementary dimensions—severity of impacts, urgency of action and capacity to respond—using the CLIMAAX evaluation dashboard as a structured analytical framework. This step is designed to support engagement with municipal experts, stakeholders and priority groups by translating quantitative modelling results into qualitative judgments that are relevant for strategic and operational decision-making.

The assessment follows a combined analytical and participatory logic, in which risk prioritisation is informed by the interaction between climate hazards, exposure and vulnerability of key systems, and the municipality's institutional, technical and financial response capacity. Uncertainties identified in the risk analysis are explicitly acknowledged and considered as part of the evaluation process. In this way, the Key Risk Assessment provides a transparent and comparable basis for prioritising climate risks and for guiding the subsequent selection of adaptation measures in Phase 3.

2.4.1 Mode of engagement for participation

Stakeholder engagement in the Key Risk Assessment for the municipality of Silistra was organised as a targeted and analytically structured process, in line with the CLIMAAX Key Risk Assessment Protocol. Building on the engagement activities conducted in Phase 1 and described in Section 2.1.5, this stage focused on the interpretation and prioritisation of already identified climate risks through a joint qualitative assessment of their severity, urgency and capacity to respond.

Engagement was carried out through focused technical consultations and structured discussions involving representatives of the municipal administration and sectoral experts with direct responsibility for climate risk management and adaptation. Participants included experts from municipal units responsible for environmental protection, spatial planning, infrastructure, agriculture, social services and civil protection, as well as specialists involved in the provision and interpretation of climate, hydrological and socio-economic data. This approach was selected to ensure that risk evaluation was informed by institutional knowledge and practical implementation experience.

Priority and vulnerable groups were represented indirectly through municipal departments responsible for social services, disaster protection and spatial planning, which incorporate the perspectives of flood-prone communities, agricultural producers and socially vulnerable populations identified during earlier stages of the assessment. This engagement model reflects the scale of the analysis and the available institutional mechanisms for representation at municipal level.

The CLIMAAX evaluation dashboard was used as the main facilitation and discussion tool, enabling participants to jointly review and interpret the risk analysis outputs in a transparent and comparable manner. Climate hazards relevant to Silistra, including agricultural drought, heavy rainfall and river flooding, were discussed in relation to severity of impacts, urgency of action and existing response capacity. The dashboard supported comparative discussion across hazards and helped to make uncertainties and data limitations explicit.

Feedback from participants confirmed the relevance of the identified key risks and their spatial concentration, particularly in the Danube floodplain and the main agricultural areas. Stakeholders highlighted constraints in response capacity, including ageing infrastructure, limited financial resources and the need for improved inter-institutional coordination. These considerations were explicitly reflected in the qualitative assessment of resilience capacity and influenced the final risk prioritisation.

Where differences in perception emerged, particularly regarding the urgency of certain risks, these were addressed through clarification of assumptions and discussion of the analytical basis of the dashboard results, rather than through formal consensus-building. Overall, the engagement process strengthened shared understanding among responsible institutions and provided a solid basis for the subsequent identification and assessment of adaptation measures in Phase 3.

Future phases of the project will further expand engagement to include a broader range of stakeholders and affected groups in the co-development of adaptation options.

2.4.2 Gather output from Risk Analysis step

The Key Risk Assessment for the municipality of Silistra is based on the systematic collection and interpretation of outputs generated during the Risk Analysis stage through the application of the CLIMAAX hazard-specific workflows. This step does not generate new quantitative analyses, but organises and contextualises existing results so that they can be used for the qualitative evaluation of severity, urgency and capacity to respond.

The risk evaluation draws on outputs related to the priority climate hazards identified for Silistra, including river flooding, heavy rainfall, agricultural drought, wind and snow. For each hazard, the assessment uses information on hazard characteristics such as intensity, frequency or probability of occurrence, spatial extent and projected future changes under different climate scenarios, as documented in Section 2.3 and the corresponding annexes.

In addition, outputs describing exposure were used, including spatial distribution of population, residential and industrial areas, agricultural land, transport and technical infrastructure, and other economic assets relevant for the municipality. These datasets allow the hazard-specific results to be interpreted in relation to the socio-economic and territorial context of Silistra.

Where available, vulnerability-related information was incorporated, reflecting social, economic and institutional characteristics such as dependence on climate-sensitive sectors, demographic features and existing limitations in response and adaptation capacity. In cases where quantitative indicators were limited, vulnerability aspects were considered qualitatively, in line with the CLIMAAX Framework.

All relevant outputs from the Risk Analysis stage were synthesised and presented in a format suitable for interpretation and discussion by stakeholders, primarily through the CLIMAAX evaluation dashboard. This structured presentation enabled a consistent comparison of hazards and provided the analytical basis for the subsequent assessment of severity, urgency and capacity to respond within the Key Risk Assessment.

2.4.3 Assess Severity

The assessment of risk severity for the municipality of Silistra combines quantitative outputs from the Risk Analysis stage with expert and institutional judgment, in line with the CLIMAAX Key Risk Assessment Protocol. Severity reflects the magnitude and scale of impacts on population, economic activities, infrastructure and ecosystems, considering both historical experience and projected future trends. Severity was assessed separately for current and future risk conditions using the four protocol-defined categories: limited, moderate, substantial and critical.

Severity of current climate risks

Under current climate conditions, **agricultural drought** is assessed as a risk of **substantial severity** for Silistra. Historical observations and recent experience confirm recurring and significant impacts on agriculture, which is a key economic sector for the municipality. Yield losses, damage to crops and increasing financial stress for farmers have been repeatedly observed, affecting livelihoods and local economic stability. While impacts are spatially widespread, they do not yet lead to irreversible loss of agricultural land, which justifies classification below the critical level.

River flooding and heavy rainfall are also assessed as risks of **substantial severity** under current conditions. Flood events and intense precipitation episodes lead to repeated damage to residential

and industrial buildings, agricultural land, transport infrastructure and technical systems, particularly in the Danube floodplain, the Aydemir lowland and low-lying settlement areas. Although catastrophic events are episodic rather than annual, the combination of high exposure, concentrated impacts and limited recovery capacity results in significant disruption of services and economic activities.

Wind-related hazards are assessed as having **limited severity** under current conditions. Available analyses indicate low wind intensities, limited spatial extent of impacts and negligible recorded damages.

Snow-related hazards are also assessed as **limited severity**, as extreme snowfall and blizzard events occur infrequently and typically cause only short-term and manageable disruptions.

Severity of future climate risks

Under future climate conditions, severity is projected to increase for several key risks. **Agricultural drought** is assessed as reaching **critical severity**, driven by projected increases in temperature, longer and more frequent dry periods and substantial yield reductions for key crops, particularly maize and sunflower. These trends indicate a high risk of long-term degradation of agricultural systems, reduced soil fertility, economic losses and increasing socio-economic vulnerability in rural areas. The cumulative and slow-onset nature of drought impacts increases the likelihood of irreversible consequences, including abandonment of agricultural land and persistent income loss.

River flooding and heavy rainfall are assessed as moving from substantial to **critical severity** under future conditions. Climate projections indicate an increased likelihood of more intense precipitation events, potentially affecting larger areas simultaneously. Potential impacts include severe damage to critical infrastructure, significant financial losses and prolonged recovery periods. The accumulation of damages over time and the exposure of strategic assets increase the risk of cascading effects, such as disruption of transport, water supply and electricity services, as well as secondary health and environmental impacts.

Wind-related risks remain assessed as **limited severity** in future scenarios. Although individual strong wind events may cause localised damage, available projections do not indicate a significant increase in frequency or intensity sufficient to elevate wind to a higher severity category at municipal scale.

Snow-related risks are likewise assessed as **limited severity** in the future, as projections consistently show decreasing frequency and intensity of heavy snowfall and blizzard events due to rising temperatures.

Cascading effects and irreversible consequences

Several of the assessed risks, particularly droughts, floods and heavy rainfall, have the potential to generate cascading and long-term effects. Prolonged droughts may lead to soil degradation, loss of biodiversity and long-term decline in agricultural productivity. Floods and intense rainfall can result in structural damage to infrastructure requiring large-scale reconstruction rather than simple repair. Combined impacts can increase pressure on municipal finances, weaken response capacity and exacerbate social vulnerability, especially among elderly populations and economically disadvantaged households.

Role of expert and stakeholder perspectives

The inclusion of perspectives from municipal experts, sector specialists and representatives of units working with vulnerable groups enriched the severity assessment by highlighting impacts not fully captured by quantitative models. Technical experts emphasised infrastructure vulnerabilities and limitations in water management systems, contributing to higher severity assessments under future scenarios. Representatives of social services drew attention to disproportionate impacts on elderly and socially vulnerable populations. Discussions also revealed uneven levels of preparedness and understanding of long-term climate risks among decision-makers, which was considered in adopting a cautious and realistic classification of future severity.

Summary of severity assessment

Overall, the severity assessment confirms that **agricultural drought, river flooding and heavy rainfall** represent risks of **substantial severity under current conditions**, escalating to **critical severity under future climate scenarios** for the municipality of Silistra. **Wind and snow** remain risks of **limited severity** in both current and future contexts. This severity assessment provides a robust basis for subsequent evaluation of urgency, resilience capacity and final risk prioritisation.

2.4.4 Assess Urgency

The assessment of urgency evaluates how soon action is required to reduce or avoid negative impacts of climate risks for the municipality of Silistra. Urgency reflects changes in severity between current and future conditions, the timing and persistence of impacts, the speed of onset of hazardous events, and the time required to implement effective adaptation measures. Urgency was assessed for each risk using the four categories defined in the CLIMAAX Key Risk Assessment Protocol: no action needed, watching brief, more action needed, and immediate action needed.

River flooding

For river flooding, urgency is assessed as **watching brief / more action needed**. Under current conditions, flood risk is moderated by existing flood protection infrastructure, particularly dikes along the Danube River, which significantly reduce the likelihood of large-scale inundation. Flood events are generally slow-onset, as high water waves propagate from upstream sections of the river basin, providing lead time for early warning and emergency response.

Future projections do not indicate a significant increase in flood severity at local scale, and in some scenarios flood heights are projected to remain stable or slightly decrease. However, the very large upstream catchment of the Danube introduces uncertainty linked to climatic developments outside the municipality. Flooding is a recurring phenomenon with potentially high impacts if protection systems fail. Stakeholder feedback confirms the effectiveness of existing infrastructure but highlights the importance of continuous maintenance and periodic upgrading. These factors support an urgency classification that emphasises monitoring and medium-term preparedness rather than immediate large-scale intervention.

Heavy rainfall

Heavy rainfall is assessed as a risk with **immediate action needed**. Under current conditions, intense precipitation events already cause surface flooding, damage to buildings and infrastructure, and

disruption of services. Climate projections consistently indicate an increase in the frequency and intensity of such events in the near to medium term.

Heavy rainfall events are sudden-onset and difficult to forecast at local scale, leaving little time for response once they occur. Although individual events are short in duration, their recurrence throughout the year—particularly during the warm season—creates persistent pressure on drainage systems and urban infrastructure. Stakeholders emphasised that most measures to date have been reactive rather than preventive. The combination of increasing severity, short reaction times and insufficient preventive infrastructure justifies the classification of heavy rainfall as requiring immediate action.

Agricultural drought

Agricultural drought is also assessed as a risk with **immediate action needed**. Current drought conditions already affect agricultural production, and future scenarios indicate a significant increase in both frequency and duration of drought periods due to rising temperatures and reduced soil moisture availability.

Drought is a slow-onset hazard, but its impacts are persistent and cumulative, affecting multiple growing seasons and progressively undermining agricultural productivity and economic stability. Effective adaptation measures, such as irrigation development, crop diversification and changes in farming practices, require long lead times for planning and implementation. Stakeholder input from agricultural representatives and municipal planners highlighted the absence of irrigation infrastructure and increasing crop losses, reinforcing the need for early and proactive intervention despite the gradual nature of the hazard.

Wind and snow

Wind-related and snow-related hazards are assessed with **no action needed / watching brief** in terms of urgency. Under current conditions, impacts are limited in scale and duration, and future projections do not indicate a substantial increase in severity or frequency at municipal level.

These hazards are generally sudden-onset but episodic, with impacts that are short-lived and manageable through existing emergency and maintenance procedures. Stakeholder feedback confirms that current preparedness and response mechanisms are adequate, although continued monitoring and routine maintenance of infrastructure remain necessary. These characteristics support a low urgency classification relative to other assessed risks.

Summary of urgency assessment

In summary, urgency differs markedly across the assessed risks. **Heavy rainfall and agricultural drought** require **immediate action** due to increasing future severity, persistence of impacts and long implementation times for effective adaptation. **River flooding** requires a **watching brief / more action needed** approach, focused on monitoring, maintenance and preparedness rather than immediate expansion of protection measures. **Wind and snow** represent risks with **low urgency**, where continued monitoring within existing management frameworks is sufficient. This urgency assessment provides a clear basis for the subsequent evaluation of resilience capacity and final risk prioritisation.

2.4.5 Understand Resilience Capacity

The assessment of resilience capacity for the municipality of Silistra was conducted in accordance with the CLIMAAX Key Risk Assessment Protocol, using the four qualitative categories: low, medium, substantial and high capacity. The assessment considers existing climate risk management measures, institutional arrangements and resources that contribute to the municipality's ability to prevent, absorb, respond to and recover from climate-related impacts. Both current capacity and expected developments over time were taken into account, drawing on documentary analysis, outputs from the Risk Analysis stage, expert judgment and stakeholder feedback.

Existing climate risk management measures

At the institutional level, the municipality of Silistra has an established framework for disaster risk management, including a Municipal Disaster Protection Plan aligned with regional and national systems. Operational response is supported by the Regional Directorate "Fire Safety and Population Protection" and the Unified Rescue System, which provide coordination and emergency response capacity for floods, intense rainfall, strong winds and winter conditions.

Physical and technical measures include national meteorological monitoring and early warning systems that are accessible at local level, as well as existing flood protection infrastructure along the Danube River. However, parts of the drainage, water management and protective infrastructure—particularly in older neighbourhoods and low-lying areas—are outdated or insufficient to cope with increasing future extremes, which limits overall physical resilience.

Capacity assessment across key dimensions

Financial capacity is assessed as **limited to medium**. While the municipality is able to mobilise resources for emergency response and recovery, it lacks sufficient own financial means for large-scale preventive investments and long-term adaptation measures. Implementation of major infrastructure upgrades, irrigation systems and nature-based solutions depends largely on national and European funding, creating constraints for proactive risk reduction.

Human capacity is assessed as **medium**. The municipality benefits from experienced staff in disaster protection and emergency management. At the same time, stakeholder discussions revealed uneven levels of climate literacy and limited experience in interpreting long-term climate scenarios and cascading risks, which constrains strategic adaptation planning.

Physical capacity is assessed as **medium**, reflecting the presence of early warning systems and emergency services, but also structural weaknesses in drainage systems, irrigation infrastructure and ageing assets exposed to climate hazards.

Social capacity is assessed as **medium**. Local non-governmental organisations, community centres and municipal social services support communication and assistance to vulnerable groups, including elderly populations and low-income households. However, citizen and business involvement in climate adaptation planning is not yet systematic, limiting broader community-based resilience.

Natural capacity is assessed as **moderate**. Agricultural land, river ecosystems and protected areas provide opportunities for nature-based solutions and ecosystem services that can reduce climate risks. At the same time, ongoing soil degradation, water stress and biodiversity loss—particularly under drought conditions—reduce the buffering capacity of natural systems.

Capacity by key risk

Overall resilience capacity varies by risk. Capacity to respond to **river flooding** is assessed as **substantial**, due to existing flood protection infrastructure, emergency response mechanisms and early warning systems, although long-term adaptation remains dependent on maintenance and external funding.

Capacity to address **heavy rainfall** is assessed as **medium**, constrained by insufficient drainage capacity and limited preventive infrastructure.

Capacity to cope with **agricultural drought** is assessed as **low to medium**, reflecting the absence of irrigation systems, high dependence on rain-fed agriculture and limited diversification options.

Capacity related to **wind and snow** is assessed as **substantial to high**, as impacts are limited and existing preparedness and response mechanisms are generally adequate.

Planned and emerging interventions

Several interventions are planned or under development that have the potential to strengthen resilience capacity in the future. These include improvements in water management and irrigation planning, integration of climate risk considerations into municipal strategic and spatial planning documents, capacity-building and training for municipal staff and stakeholders, and participation in projects such as CLIMAAX that provide methodological, analytical and networking support. However, these interventions are not yet fully implemented and, at present, are insufficient to elevate overall resilience capacity to a high level across all risk dimensions.

Summary of resilience capacity assessment

In summary, the resilience capacity of the municipality of Silistra with respect to its main climate risks is assessed as **medium to substantial**, depending on the specific hazard and capacity dimension considered. Strong institutional foundations and operational emergency response coexist with key weaknesses related to financial resources, ageing infrastructure and limited integration of long-term climate adaptation into local planning. These capacity gaps play a decisive role in the prioritisation of risks and highlight the need for targeted investments and policy measures, which are addressed in the subsequent phase of the project.

2.4.6 Decide on Risk Priority

The prioritisation of climate risks for the municipality of Silistra was carried out qualitatively, in accordance with the CLIMAAX Key Risk Assessment Protocol, by integrating the outcomes of the severity, urgency and resilience capacity assessments. Risk priority was not determined through numerical aggregation, but through structured expert judgement supported by stakeholder input and guided by the CLIMAAX evaluation dashboard.

The prioritisation process followed the logic of the CLIMAAX evaluation matrix, whereby risks characterised by high or increasing severity, high urgency and low to medium resilience capacity are assigned higher priority for action. Particular attention was paid to the distinction between current and future risk, with hazards showing moderate current but critical future impacts identified as strategic priorities for long-term adaptation planning.

The CLIMAAX evaluation dashboard was used as the main synthesis tool to compare risks across the three dimensions. For each hazard, qualitative ratings for current and future severity, urgency and resilience capacity were entered into the dashboard, together with short justifications reflecting the local context of Silistra. This allowed a transparent comparison of risks and made explicit the trade-offs between impact magnitude, timing of action and existing response capacity.

Based on this integrated assessment, **agricultural drought and heavy rainfall** are identified as **very high priority risks** for the municipality of Silistra. These risks combine substantial to critical future severity, immediate or growing urgency and low to medium resilience capacity, particularly in relation to financial resources, irrigation and drainage infrastructure, and adaptive capacity in agriculture. Their impacts affect multiple key systems simultaneously, including agricultural production, population livelihoods, economic assets and ecosystem functions, and have strong potential for cascading and long-term socio-economic consequences.

River flooding is classified as a **high priority risk**. While existing flood protection infrastructure and early warning systems provide a degree of protection, the exposure of the Danube floodplain, the concentration of assets in low-lying areas and the potential for high-impact events justify continued prioritisation. The risk requires sustained attention through monitoring, maintenance of protection infrastructure and preparedness measures, rather than immediate large-scale expansion of defences.

Snow-related hazards and strong winds are assessed as **lower priority risks**. Although they can cause local and episodic damage, their overall severity and urgency are limited, and existing operational response capacity is relatively well developed. These risks are therefore best addressed through routine preparedness, monitoring and targeted preventive measures rather than through major strategic adaptation investments.

Overall, the prioritisation reflects not only the magnitude and likelihood of climate impacts, but also the municipality's actual capacity to respond and adapt. The result of the Key Risk Assessment is a clear and justified basis for directing adaptation planning, investment and policy development in Phase 3, aligned with the specific vulnerabilities, constraints and opportunities of the municipality of Silistra.

Table 2.3 – Key Risks Dashboard

Risk Workflow	Severity		Urgency	Capacity	Risk Priority
	C	F		Resilience/ CRM	
River flooding	Critical	Substantial	Immediate action needed	Substantial	HIGH
Heavy rainfall	Critical	Substantial	More action needed	Substantial	VERY HIGH
Drought	Critical	Substantial	Watching brief	Substantial	VERY HIGH
Snow	Limited	Limited	No action needed	High	LOW
Wind	Limited	Limited	No action needed	High	LOW

Severity Critical Substantial Moderate Limited	Urgency Immediate action needed More action needed Watching brief No action needed	Resilience Capacity High Substantial Medium Low	Risk Ranking Very high High Moderate Low
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Table 2.4. CLIMAAX Key Risk Assessment – Final prioritisation for Silistra

Risk Workflow	Hazard description	Affected areas / sectors	Severity – Current	Severity – Future	Urgency	Resilience capacity	Capacity justification
River flooding	Flooding caused by high water levels of the Danube River and tributaries	Danube floodplain, Aydemir lowland, residential and industrial areas, agricultural land, transport and utilities	Substantial	Substantial–Critical	Watching brief / More action needed	Medium–Substantial	Existing flood protection, early warning and emergency response systems are in place, but ageing infrastructure, maintenance needs and exposure of assets constrain long-term adaptive capacity
Heavy rainfall	Short-duration and daily extreme precipitation events causing surface flooding	Urban areas, drainage systems, transport infrastructure, agriculture	Substantial	Critical	Immediate action needed	Medium	Limited drainage capacity, insufficient preventive infrastructure and reliance on reactive measures
Agricultural drought	Prolonged low precipitation combined with rising temperatures	Agricultural land, rural settlements, water resources, local economy	Substantial	Critical	Immediate action needed	Low–Medium	Absence of irrigation systems, high dependence on rain-fed agriculture, limited financial and technical capacity
Snow	Heavy snowfall and frost events	Transport infrastructure, rural settlements, agriculture	Limited	Limited	No action needed / Watching brief	Substantial	Established winter response procedures and declining future hazard
Wind	Strong winds and storm events	Agricultural land, buildings, power supply	Limited	Limited	No action needed / Watching brief	Substantial	Limited exposure and impacts; adequate operational preparedness

Explanatory notes

- **Severity** reflects quantified and qualitative impacts from the Risk Analysis, including effects on population, infrastructure, agriculture and ecosystems, and the potential for cascading and irreversible impacts.
- **Urgency** reflects changes between current and future risk, timing of impacts, persistence and the speed of onset of hazards.
- **Resilience capacity** integrates financial, human, physical, natural and social dimensions, including existing measures and known constraints.
- **Risk priority** is assigned qualitatively, based on the combined severity–urgency–capacity profile, in line with the CLIMAAX Key Risk Assessment Protocol and supported by the evaluation dashboard.

2.5 Monitoring and Evaluation

Section 2.5 reflects on the outcomes of Phase 2 of the Climate Risk Assessment, focusing on lessons learned, challenges encountered, stakeholder feedback and implications for monitoring and evaluation. The section addresses how learning is ensured, what data gaps remain, how risks will be monitored over time and how the results of the CRA are intended to inform policy, planning and investment decisions. Particular attention is given to the monitoring of risks identified as high and very high priority in Section 2.4.

The second phase of the climate risk assessment provided information on both the nature of climate risks in the municipality of Silistra and the institutional and social capacity to manage them. One of the main conclusions is that climate risks in Silistra are structural and cumulative, not isolated events. Droughts, floods on the Danube River and intense rainfall interact with the agricultural structure of the economy, demographic processes and the state of the infrastructure, leading to cumulative and sometimes cascading impacts. Phase 2 clearly demonstrated the added value of a structured risk assessment through the CLIMAAX Key Risk Assessment Protocol, which allowed for transparent and reasoned prioritization of risks based on severity, urgency and response capacity. Unlike Phase 1, where the focus was on identification and methodological implementation, Phase 2 showed that it is precisely the limited response capacity that is a key factor in the high risk in Silistra.

The most significant difficulties were related to the limited availability of high-resolution and locally calibrated climate and hydrological data, as well as inconsistencies between different data sources and scales of analysis. There were also some challenges in engaging a wider range of local stakeholders, especially from rural areas and the agricultural sector. These limitations were addressed through qualitative expert interpretation, iterative discussions with municipal specialists and combining quantitative results with local knowledge, in line with the recommendations of the CLIMAAX Handbook.

Stakeholders play a central role in Monitoring and Evaluation, especially in validating the significance of risks, interpreting impacts and directing results towards policies. Representatives of the municipal administration, the agricultural sector, social services and civil society organizations stressed the need for clearer communication of future climate scenarios, a stronger link between CRA results and strategic documents and investment decisions of the municipality. The need for continued involvement beyond the assessment phase, including in implementation and monitoring, was also highlighted. This feedback directly informs the design of the monitoring framework and strengthens the link between risk prioritisation and policy implementation.

The adaptability of the process is ensured by documenting assumptions, uncertainties and gaps in the data and by providing feedback between analysis, assessment and decision-making. The CRA is treated as a “living process” that can be updated as new data, tools or policies become available. The results of the Climate Risk Assessment will be communicated through municipal strategic documents, internal coordination mechanisms, and targeted dissemination to relevant stakeholders, including sectoral departments, emergency services and agricultural representatives. Key findings will also be used to support applications for national and European funding and to raise awareness of priority climate risks among decision-makers and the public.

Phase 2 identifies new opportunities for using satellite data on land use, vegetation and water bodies, improved socio-economic indicators and qualitative information from local stakeholders.

At the same time, critical needs remain for more detailed data on precipitation, drought and water resources, mapping of critical infrastructure, economic damage assessment and analysis of social vulnerability and secondary effects.

Currently, the municipality of Silistra does not have a fully integrated climate risk monitoring system. Existing disaster protection and early warning mechanisms provide a baseline, but an upgrade is

needed. The recommended reassessment period is every 5–10 years for key risks (drought, floods), as well as ad hoc for significant climate events.

Resources were used effectively within the available constraints. The focus on priority risks had a positive effect on the clarity and applicability of the CRA, but limited the depth of the modelling. The conclusion is that the impact of the CRA on the municipality of Silistra will be significant due to increased institutional awareness, better understanding of the risk and better readiness to direct future investments and funding, given the specifics of the municipality and the conclusion on climate vulnerability.

The monitoring framework established in this section provides the basis for tracking the effectiveness of adaptation measures to be developed in Phase 3 and for updating the risk assessment as new data and experience become available.

Table 2.5. Monitoring framework

Risk Workflow	Indicator Category	Indicator	Measure / Unit	Baseline / Observed Value	Target / Monitoring Plan	Data Source / Frequency
Drought & High Temperatures	Temperature extremes	Days with temperature $\geq 35^{\circ}\text{C}$	days/year	~15–25 days/year; max up to $39\text{--}40^{\circ}\text{C}$; documented drought losses	Track annual trend and exceedance of historical average	NIMH temperature records / Annual
River Flooding	River water levels	Days above critical Danube water level	days/year	Critical level 785 cm; flood events already occurring in current climate	Early warning and reduced exposure	Danube hydrological records / Annual
Heavy Rainfall	Extreme precipitation	Rainfall per event	mm/event	~50 mm/24h threshold; agricultural & urban flood impacts	Track number of >80 mm events per year	NIMH precipitation records / Annual
Strong Winds & Storms	Wind intensity	Maximum wind speed	m/s	73 storm events; 646.24 ha fully damaged	Track frequency of high-wind events	NIMH wind data / Annual

For Silistra Municipality, the monitoring framework covers a broad range of climate hazards identified as relevant through the CLIMAAX risk exploration phase. While the indicator structure is

fully defined for all risk workflows, baseline values are currently incomplete for several indicators due to data availability constraints. These gaps are explicitly documented and will be addressed through improved local data collection and monitoring in subsequent project phases.

In addition, below we present a table summarizing a set of key indicators used to monitor climate risks, vulnerability and adaptive capacity of the territory. The indicators cover both the physical manifestations of climate hazards and the social and institutional factors that determine the degree of impact and the ability to respond.

- ✓ Drought. Years with prolonged dry periods. The indicator reports the frequency of years with prolonged dry periods, with the observed increasing trend after 2020 reflecting the increasing risk of droughts in the region. Monitoring through an annual agrometeorological survey allows the identification of long-term trends and their relationship with agricultural production, water resources and soil degradation.
- ✓ Flooding. Flood incidents along the Danube. This indicator measures the occurrence of floods along the Danube River, based on event reporting when specific incidents occur. The approach allows for rapid documentation of real impacts and supports the analysis of the relationship between hydrological conditions, extreme precipitation and local exposure of the territory.
- ✓ Agriculture. Damaged agricultural land. The indicator reflects damage to agricultural land caused by climate extremes, including droughts and floods. Data on documented crop losses, collected through annual agricultural statistics, provide a quantitative basis for assessing the economic consequences and for monitoring the effectiveness of adaptation measures in the sector.
- ✓ Vulnerability. Elderly population in risk zones. This indicator measures social vulnerability through the share of the elderly population living in areas with increased climate risk. The high relative share of this group increases the sensitivity of the community to climate events, especially floods and heat waves. Combining demographic data from the census with risk maps allows for spatially precise assessment and helps to target protection and preparedness measures.

Table 2.6. Monitoring indicators

Indicator Category	Indicator	Baseline / Observed	Monitoring Approach
Drought	Years with prolonged dry periods	Increasing frequency (post-2020)	Annual agrometeorological review
Flooding	Flood incidents along Danube	Periodic local flooding	Event-based reporting
Agriculture	Damaged agricultural land	Documented crop losses	Annual agricultural statistics
Vulnerability	Elderly population in risk zones	High share	Census + risk maps (5–10 yrs)
Institutional capacity	Training on climate risk	Ad hoc	Training, good practices sharing

2.6 Work plan Phase 3

The objective of Phase 3 is to translate the refined climate risk assessment results from Phase 2 into a targeted set of adaptation options that respond to Silistra's specific territorial, socio-economic and institutional context. This phase focuses on prioritising actions that are feasible under conditions of limited demographic, financial and administrative capacity, while addressing the most significant climate risks identified for the municipality.

Main activities include:

Activity 3.1 – Consolidation of key risk assessment findings.

The first activity in Phase 3 will consolidate the key findings from the multi-risk assessment, with particular emphasis on:

- risks related to river flooding and intense precipitation along the Danube and low-lying areas;
- increasing drought and heat stress affecting agricultural production and water resources;
- combined impacts on ageing populations, rural settlements and critical municipal infrastructure.

This consolidation step ensures that adaptation planning is grounded in clearly defined risk priorities, rather than addressing climate hazards in isolation.

Activity 3.2 – Identification of context-specific adaptation measures.

Based on the prioritised risks, the project will identify potential adaptation measures tailored to Silistra's local conditions, drawing on:

CLIMAAX guidance on adaptation pathways;

- national and regional climate adaptation strategies;
- relevant good practices from comparable agricultural and riverine regions.

The measures will address both risk reduction and adaptive capacity.

Activity 3.3 – Screening and prioritisation of adaptation options.

Identified measures will be screened using qualitative criteria, including:

- relevance to the specific risk drivers identified in Phase 2;
- feasibility under current institutional and financial constraints;
- potential co-benefits for local development and ecosystem resilience.

This process will result in a prioritised and realistic set of adaptation options, distinguishing between short-term "no-regret" measures and longer-term strategic actions.

Phase 3 explicitly follows up on the outcomes of the risk assessment by:

- linking each adaptation option to specific hazards, exposed systems and vulnerable groups;
- documenting how the proposed measures address the underlying causes of risk, such as demographic decline, land-use patterns and water stress;
- ensuring traceability between Phase 2 risk priorities and Phase 3 adaptation outputs.

This approach ensures coherence between assessment and action and strengthens the usability of the results for municipal decision-making. Aspects not studied and justification Phase 3 does not include:

- detailed technical design or engineering studies of adaptation measures;
- implementation planning beyond strategic prioritisation.

These aspects are excluded because the CLIMAAX framework focuses on strategic exploration of adaptation options, while detailed design and implementation require separate processes, additional data and dedicated funding instruments beyond the project's scope.

The outcome of Phase 3 is a context-sensitive portfolio of prioritised adaptation options for Silistra Municipality, directly linked to the most critical climate risks and socio-economic vulnerabilities identified in Phase 2. These results provide a solid foundation for future integration into municipal planning documents and the development of targeted implementation projects.

3 Conclusions Phase 2 - Climate risk assessment

The climate risk assessment confirms that the municipality of Silistra is highly exposed to **water-related and temperature-related climate hazards**, with **agricultural drought, heavy rainfall and river flooding** identified as the most relevant risks under current and future climate conditions. The municipality's location along the Danube River, its predominantly agricultural economic structure and its demographic profile strongly influence both exposure and vulnerability.

A central conclusion of Phase 2 is that **agricultural drought represents a structural and long-term risk** for Silistra. Under future climate scenarios, drought severity is projected to reach critical levels due to increasing temperatures, longer and more frequent dry periods and high dependence on rain-fed agriculture. Limited irrigation infrastructure and constrained financial capacity further amplify this risk, increasing the likelihood of persistent economic losses and long-term degradation of agricultural systems.

Heavy rainfall is identified as a **very high priority risk**, characterised by increasing frequency and intensity of extreme precipitation events, sudden onset and limited response time. Projected exceedance of damage thresholds poses growing risks to urban areas, drainage systems and transport infrastructure, with high urgency for preventive and adaptive measures.

River flooding along the Danube remains a **high-priority risk**, with substantial impacts already observed in flood-prone areas such as the Aydemir lowland and riverfront zones. While existing flood protection infrastructure and early warning systems moderate immediate risk, the high exposure of population, economic assets and infrastructure, combined with uncertainty related to upstream hydrological processes, justifies continued prioritisation through monitoring, maintenance and preparedness.

The assessment further demonstrates that climate risks in Silistra are **unevenly distributed**, with specific settlements, neighbourhoods and social groups facing disproportionately higher exposure and lower adaptive capacity. Elderly populations, rural communities and low-income households are particularly vulnerable, reinforcing the need for targeted and socially sensitive adaptation planning.

Overall ranking of priority climate risks

Table 3.1. Overall prioritisation of climate risks for the municipality of Silistra

Rank	Climate risk	Overall priority level	Key drivers of risk	Main affected receptors
1	Agricultural drought	Very high	Increasing duration and frequency of dry periods; high dependence on rain-fed agriculture; limited irrigation and adaptive capacity	Agricultural production, farmers' income, rural economy
2	Heavy rainfall	Very high	Increasing intensity and frequency of extreme precipitation; sudden-onset events; insufficient drainage capacity	Urban areas, transport and drainage infrastructure, buildings
3	River flooding	High	Exposure of floodplain areas; concentration of population and assets; reliance on ageing flood protection infrastructure	Population, buildings, critical infrastructure, agricultural and industrial land

Rank	Climate risk	Overall priority level	Key drivers of risk	Main affected receptors
4	Snow	Low	Low historical frequency; declining future occurrence; limited spatial extent	Population, transport (episodic disruptions)
5	Wind	Low	Limited intensity and impacts; adequate operational preparedness	Built environment (minor, localised impacts)

Key findings

- **Escalation of risks over time:** Agricultural drought and heavy rainfall show a clear increase in severity from current to future scenarios, driven by rising temperatures and intensifying precipitation extremes.
- **High exposure of critical assets:** Agricultural land, residential areas, transport networks and technical infrastructure located in low-lying and river-adjacent zones are particularly exposed to flooding and intense rainfall.
- **Social vulnerability as a risk multiplier:** Demographic trends and socio-economic characteristics increase sensitivity to climate impacts, amplifying overall risk beyond physical exposure alone.
- **Sudden- and slow-onset dynamics:** Heavy rainfall presents sudden-onset risks with limited response time, while drought represents a slow-onset but persistent hazard requiring early and sustained intervention.
- **Potential for cascading impacts:** Key risks may trigger secondary effects such as infrastructure failure, disruption of economic activities, public health risks and long recovery periods.
- **Stakeholder alignment:** Feedback from municipal experts and stakeholders confirms the prioritisation of drought, heavy rainfall and flooding and highlights constraints in response capacity as a critical factor shaping risk.

Challenges and limitations

Phase 2 addressed several methodological and practical challenges, including the application of a consistent and transparent framework for assessing current and future risks at municipal scale and the integration of European climate datasets with local exposure and vulnerability information. At the same time, limitations remain and are acknowledged as areas for further development, including constraints in high-resolution socio-economic data, limited assessment of compound and cascading risks, and the focus on a selected set of priority hazards.

Overall conclusion

Phase 2 successfully delivered a robust, locally grounded and policy-relevant climate risk assessment for the municipality of Silistra. The results clearly demonstrate that **agricultural drought, heavy rainfall and river flooding** constitute the most significant climate risks, driven not only by hazard characteristics but also by limited resilience capacity and high exposure of key systems.

The findings provide a clear and justified analytical foundation for **Phase 3**, where adaptation measures will be identified, assessed and prioritised in direct response to the risks and vulnerabilities identified in this phase, with a focus on reducing long-term impacts, strengthening resilience and supporting sustainable local development.

4 Progress evaluation

Table 4.1 Overview key performance indicators

Key performance indicators	Progress
1 climate multi-risk assessment report published (month 6 and Month 16)	Deliverable 1 submitted on 31.03.2025 Deliverable 2 submitted on 19.01.2026
10000 residents, key local and regional authorities, and stakeholders reached through awareness campaigns (Month 22)	Pending
2 workshops, one final conference and meetings conducted for decision-makers (Months 2, 6, 15, 22)	Organized and conducted kick-off meeting with the project team, municipal stakeholders and external experts. Workshop 1 for stakeholders – 28.03.2025 Workshop 2 for decision makers – 15.01.2026
Municipal strategic documents on disaster management and environmental management reviewed and revised (Month 21)	Pending
At least 1 risk management measure integrated into local development planning (Month 21)	Pending
Preparing outline for a long-term climate resilience strategy (Month 21)	Pending
1 media/press conference (Month 2)	Initial press-conference – 24.10.2024
5 publications on the website of the municipality for the project (Months 2, 6, 16, 21, 22)	Press releases on the website of Silistra Municipality (Months 2, 6, 16): https://silistra.egov.bg/wps/portal/municipality-silistra/actual/news/vstupitelna-preskonferenciya-proekt https://silistra.egov.bg/wps/portal/municipality-silistra/administration/projects/pokana-seminar https://silistra.egov.bg/wps/portal/municipality-silistra/actual/news/seminar-klimaks https://silistra.egov.bg/wps/portal/municipality-silistra/actual/news/seminar-doklad-proekt

Key performance indicators	Progress
	https://www.facebook.com/municipality.silistra/?locale=bg_BG
2 communication actions taken to share results with stakeholders – 1 workshop and 1 final conference (Months 15, 22).	Workshop 2 for decision makers – 15.01.2026

Table 4.2 Overview milestones

Milestones	Progress
M1: Completion of the review of local legal, financial, and administrative frameworks with recommendations for improvement (Month 5)	Completed on 14.03.2025
M2: Kick-off meeting of the project team with municipal and external experts (Month 2)	Completed
M3: Press conference to announce the project and its goals (Month 2)	Completed on 24.10.2024
M4: Completion of the workshop on the application and adaptation of the CLIMAAX framework (Month 6)	Completed on 28.03.2025
M5: Submission and acceptance of the report on the application and adaptation of the CLIMAAX framework (Month 6)	Submitted on 31.03.2025
M6: Attend the CLIMAAX workshop held in Barcelona (Month 10)	Completed on 10-11.06.2025
M7: Completion of the desktop research on municipal, regional, and national data related to climate risks and vulnerable sectors (Month 14)	Completed by 31.12.2025
M8: Workshop with local and national stakeholders to gather additional data and insights (Month 15)	Completed on 15.01.2026
M9: Submission and acceptance of the report on multi-risk assessment results (Month 16)	Submitted on 19.01.2026

<i>Milestones</i>	<i>Progress</i>
M10: Completion of the review and revision of the municipal disaster risk reduction program based on multi-risk and vulnerabilities identified (Month 19)	Pending
M11: Amendments to the Ordinance on Disaster and Accidents Management and municipal strategic documents (Month 21)	Pending
M12: Attend the CLIMAAX workshop held in Brussels (December 2026)	Pending
M13: Final conference on project results to disseminate findings and recommendations (Month 22)	Pending

5 Supporting documentation

Annexes

1. *Detailed hazard and risk analysis*
 - *Annex A – River Floods*
 - *Annex B – Heavy Rainfall*
 - *Annex C – Agricultural Drought*
 - *Annex D – Wind*
 - *Annex E - Snow*

2. *Archive of customized Jupyter Notebooks*

6 References

European and CLIMAAX framework documents

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6. **Valcheva, R., Spiridonov, V.** (2019).
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13. **Municipality of Silistra** (2023).
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14. **Ministry of Agriculture and Food (2025).**
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Available at: <https://www.mzh.government.bg>
15. **Ministry of Agriculture and Food (2021).**
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16. **National Statistical Institute (NSI) (2023).**
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Sofia.
17. **Institute for Market Economics (IME) (2025).**
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Supporting scientific and technical sources

18. **ECMWF (2023).**
ERA5 Reanalysis Dataset – Documentation and Applications.
Copernicus Climate Change Service.
19. **Meteoalarm (2023).**
Thresholds for severe weather warnings in Europe.
European Meteorological Network.

Legal framework

20. **Republic of Bulgaria (2006, as amended).**
Disaster Protection Act.
21. **Republic of Bulgaria (2014, as amended).**
Climate Change Mitigation Act.
22. **Republic of Bulgaria (2001, as amended).**
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